

WAYS TO INCREASE ENTERPRISE PROFIT IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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1. Introduction

The knowledge of business landscape helps people to understand the given opportunities and threats. Every company is a part of one or more segments of a business and these segments are known as industries. For example, my own company is a part of the cosmetic industry. As stated by FCIB (2015), the political and economic life of a country in which a business operates always has a big impact on the performance of that business. Furthermore, the social life and the natural environment in that country also have an equal impact on the profitability of that business. In the USA, people always prefer to use cosmetics while in the UK, the trend of using cosmetics is less as compared to the USA (Doran, 2014). The use of social media and networking sites is increasing nowadays and businesses use social media to promote their products and to reach the customers (Koehn et al., 2012). In order to identify where the biggest opportunities lie and the biggest threats for my company are, we need to have a good picture of the current business landscape, and that picture can be built through analyses of the given environment. Nowadays, the competition is more than ever and businesses have to be keen to develop the growth strategies and goals because the business without strategies and goals may become directionless. On the contrary to this, businesses also have to manage the risk measures because wrong decisions can lead a business to legal issues and financial losses. The strategies and goals of a business always have several options that properly define what the businesses want to achieve and how it's going to achieve. In a modern business landscape, maximizing profits through continuous improvement has become a predominant objective. In order to ensure growth and sustainability, managers of a profit-facing organization have shifted their attention to the expansion of efficiency and business excellence. Over the period of time, various strategies have been developed by the management gurus and experts in the field of business management to help in realizing this factor. Every business organization wants to improve and maximize the profit with the help of modern management science. However, the profit-making is affected by different parameters which include day-to-day operational input, managerial decisions, and sporadic strategic initiatives in either marketing, production, or the general management. Historically, organizations have always worked to maximize their output and efficiencies either by increasing the manpower, capital investment, or incorporating the latest technologies. Adapting a strategy of productivity and efficiency improvements is also a popular method which has been utilized for many years to maximize the output and to improve the profit. A core part of a successful business plan is identifying tactics that support the business strategy. This helps to ensure that the overall business plan is viable and that all the goals of the strategy can be met. When analyzing business strategies, it is very important to identify the ways or methods that a company can actually increase its profit by implementing certain technologies or methods. With the advancement in technologies and the management expertise, the businesses not only focus on the internal reforms to maximize the profit but also look at the external emerging trends and business opportunities. By doing a comprehensive environmental analysis, companies today can easily get much greater knowledge about the ways through which they can increase the profit. An environmental analysis can be best understood by recognizing the nature of the given environment of businesses such as social, political, economic, and natural environment. The environmental analysis helps the management to identify the opportunities and threats in the business.

1.1. Overview of the Current Business Landscape

By applying the strategies and techniques outlined in the article, businesses can increase their profitability and thrive in the modern business environment.

A useful way to approach this is to carry out a SWOT analysis - a review of the business's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This form of analysis provides an invaluable guide

to where a business is now and can identify where changes might be needed. Businesses that operate solely within their own borders do not have to face this form of analysis on a global scale. It can be more difficult for a business to make regular changes to products or processes for long-term benefits. However, businesses cannot assume that the strategies which have been in place, and have driven business success in the past, will continue to work in the future. New competitors may emerge, the economic climate may suffer, and consumer trends may change - so it is essential to continually revisit strategic plans.

In such a dynamic environment, it is critical for businesses to constantly evaluate their strategic positioning and find ways to adapt and succeed. This means being aware of the market in which a business operates, understanding where a business is positioned in that market, and finding ways to differentiate a business from other providers. By creating a strategy that is based on a sound understanding of the wider business landscape, a business will be better able to take advantage of the opportunities that arise.

The modern business landscape is complex and ever-changing. Globalization, rapid technological advancements, and a turbulent economic environment have resulted in new challenges for businesses. For example, both small local shops and global organizations are facing increasing competition from e-commerce businesses. Not just traditional manufacturing industries, but also modern service industries, are struggling to adopt advanced technologies such as robotics and artificial intelligence. Moreover, economic uncertainty is putting pressure on businesses to remain competitive and grow, as investors are expecting higher returns and lower risk.

1.2. Importance of Increasing Profit in Modern Conditions

Today's business world is rapidly changing. Social, political, and economic forces, combined with technological advances, have created a highly dynamic and fast-paced environment. In such an environment, the business community is continuously looking for ways to gain a competitive advantage, increase market share, and realize economies of scale. All these objectives, however, have a common focus, which is boosting profitability. Profit increase is the primary goal of any business. Profit, in the business sense, is simply the earnings that the enterprise makes after all the expenses have been deducted. This is the money that remains after the sale of goods and services and all operational costs are accounted for. There are various types of profit including gross profit, net profit, and operating profit. For the purposes of this study, profit will generally refer to the generic aspect of earnings that are made. Profit is very significant to any business. This is because it's used to measure the success of the business, making profit is also a sign of the efficient use of resource. The importance of profit increase in modern conditions cannot be underestimated. This is first and foremost because the world is moving towards globalization and industrialization at a very high speed. All the forces of globalization are resulting into extreme competition in the market. In fact, with globalization, businesses are no longer competing on local basis but on international level. This means that a company operating in Kenya is not only faced with competition from local companies but also from international entities. Globalization has also led to increase in production and this has led to firms producing more than what the local market can consume. As a result, there must be emergent ways of selling the excess production. Furthermore, profit increase is very crucial given the fact that the production process are becoming more complex due to the use of advanced technology and machinery. The cost of such technology is very high and its maintenance involves significant amount of money. As a matter of fact, most businesses are investing in modern technology with the aim that they will realize efficiency in their production. By realizing efficiency, it is anticipated that more output will be realized and hence more sales. However, realizing efficient production through modern technology requires a period of continuous improvement and this mean that the firm will require adequate finance to run its operation and adjust to market changes. This simply tells us that without profit, it is virtually impossible for companies to operate smoothly and grow from one level to another. A company's ability to increase its profit shows that it must be having a competitive advantage. When we talk about competitive advantage, we mean the ability of a business to use its best resources in a

way that it will create more customer value. Businesses that have competitive advantage are able to satisfy customers in a better way as compared to their rivals and are likely to have higher profits. For a company to be in a position to increase its profit, it must be able to apply its resources in such a way as to move from one level of profit to a higher level. This continuous increase in profit clearly shows a positive indication for long term economic growth.

2. Strategic Planning

Another vital way to increase enterprise profit in modern conditions is through strategic planning, which provides a company with the framework to make day-to-day management decisions with a sense of common goals and understanding among the management team. It sets up the means for the company to progress in a certain direction in the future in a way that the company has resources sufficient to achieve the planned progress. Strategic planning is the process by which a company identifies its long-term direction and the means to get there, achieves its mission measures progress, and communicates statement to people within organization. From doing so, strategic planning gives not only a useful tool for guiding a company, but also a way of measuring and monitoring the continuing success. According to QuickMBA.com, a specific model of strategic planning takes form in the shape of the following process: development of the business mission, analysis of the external environment in which the business operates, analysis of the company's existing resources or the internal environment, identification of the objectives of the business, development and selection of strategic choices that are most likely to achieve the objectives, translation of these strategic choices into operational plans with specific actions and objectives, and establishment of means to monitor the success of the operational plans. We will look at the strategic planning in a different perspective. In order to achieve this you will have to look at strategic planning as a three-phase work-in-progress that requires flexibility and choices. Ordering essays from custom writing services has become popular among many; however all the advantages and disadvantages of ordering essays are not yet clear. This process has to be done by the management with foresight and explicit thinking, with the aim of giving a useful framework for competitive and profitable action, but it must not be the sole province of the people at the top. It is the duty of the executive side of a company to engage the process, so that all may understand what the company is about and what it is trying to achieve, and may contribute according to their sphere of expertise and interest. In order to secure means for effective negotiation and participation in the process of strategic planning, human resource matters have to be taken into account. It is proved that employees' influence on strategic planning is by no means antithetic to the tenets of economic rationality; rather, their influence in any other organizational area is powerful, it provides an element of competent advantage. Keen and nimble competition in an increasing number of markets, whether they are international or local, means that many successful organizations undertake strategic planning of one form or another.

2.1. Identifying Business Objectives

Identifying business objectives involves a number of steps. First of all, the strategic planners need to be consulted. This may include the senior management team or sometimes business owners, depending on the size of the business. These people are usually the key decision makers and sometimes may also be the experts in running the business. By consulting with them, it is ensured that the objectives identified match the real goals of the business. In a growing and fast-changing industry, the pace of change is so fast that if you are standing still then you are gradually moving backwards. Businesses need to be proactive, and they need to give their workforce and management the necessary tools and conditions for success. Experience shows that the strategic planning which identifies the objectives and aims for the companies helps to motivate the workforce. The shared vision of the business' future among the workforce fosters the culture of continuous improvement and gives the employees an understanding of how they can contribute to the achievement of business goals. Also, identifying the business objectives is important for a variety of participants. When a new business develops, the owner's first objective is to survive. Then the focus will shift towards other objectives such as to increase profit, to employ more people, and to expand in new markets and to

win a particular reputation, etc. For someone who wants to buy an existing business or to secure finance for a new business, it is highly important to clearly know and clearly state the business's objectives. We cannot make an expert judgment by simply looking at some information down to a couple of pages into a report. The understanding of objectives is the key foundation for the development of any kind of business plan. And to the people who work in these companies, the knowledge of goals is equally important. Sharing the business plan and the business' success with employees will increase the probability of retaining the staff that the companies have invested in adequately training. Also, it contributes to the result of higher efficiency in the businesses. In this aspect, human resources managers may take charge. But from another perspective, since employees themselves know a lot of job contents and individual skills and abilities, the aims identified should also have a fair reflection of the employees' individual development. Balancing the needs of the businesses with the human resource planning is the key to the success theories of strategic planning.

2.2. Conducting a SWOT Analysis

Conducting a SWOT analysis involves evaluating the internal strengths and weaknesses of the organization and external opportunities and threats. This is a critical planning tool which is widely used in the modern business arena to find a new direction for growth and profitability. The organization needs to determine what the main purpose of the SWOT analysis is - for example, it may be used in preparation for a new business venture, diversification or expansion and might involve a particular project such as capital investment, modernization or a change in the business direction. It is important to be clear whether the objective is applying the analysis to the whole business or just part of it and to involve the right people in the process. SWOT analysis can be applied to planning, marketing, competitor analysis, business and product development, also human resources etc. During the study it was also identified that some organizations have modified their confidence, so they have called it as "slot analysis". It specifically considered the relative importance in environmental factors and the potential of the strategy in the marketing. Next, there are primary and secondary data related to the SWOT analysis. Commonly it composes of two main factors - primary and secondary. Primary data outlines the different parameter of the analysis and secondary data provide the general backgrounds, including research from customer and general studies. However, it may vary for the different organization because of their specific product and services. After pinpointing the various elements, it comes to the potential answer from the analysis. It is generally beneficial. It will lead the organization to play on the strengths and avoid to expose the weaknesses. It guides to find out the potential opportunities and to concede over the threats. It can provide an impetus to the further analysis and accommodate the future possible developments. Such technique is not only conducting in the class. As a matter of fact, following a new round of tariff, some companies turn to such analysis to find out how to adjust. IKEA discovered another opportunity in the China as the superpower fights. GAC Motor realized that they need to improve themselves to embrace the challenges from the US. As a popular cosmetic company, Clinique is facing to the changing customers' needs and that sad news for their face sales. If it keeps falling down, the company has to regroup and restrict the Cost for restructuring. Such kind of analytical tool will be elaborated more in the following chapter.

2.3. Developing a Profit-Driven Strategy

So, how does a business develop a profit-driven strategy? Firstly, it is important to identify the profit objectives of the business. There is usually a hierarchy of objectives - for example, survival, profitability, growth - and these need to be reflected in the strategy. Profit objectives should be detailed, specifying the level and timescale of the profits expected. The strategy should then seek to deliver these profit objectives at the least risk. Thus any profit-driven strategy needs to take into account the business's position in the life cycle and the general nature of the environment in which it operates, for example the level of competition and the rate of technological change. In the analysis the business's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats should be clearly related to the mission and objectives. Trends and strategic uncertainties should be identified and, where possible, quantified, and this information should guide the setting of the profit objectives and choice of strategy. Finally,

the technology used in the business should be described - both in terms of its current state of development and the direction in which it is moving - and possible future developments should be used to give an insight into where the business and its markets are going. This will help to ensure that the strategy is not only profit driven but gives a good steer on the amounts and timing of the profits anticipated. All staff should be involved in developing and delivering the profit objectives. The profit-driven strategy will generate a 'line of sight', so that everybody can see where their efforts fit into the overall plan. If a particular activity is not going to contribute to the profit objectives, then there will be good reason to question whether that activity should be done at all. It should be made clear that 'profit' does not necessarily mean 'cash'. When developing a profit-driven strategy, perhaps the most difficult thing is to get the balance right. Too woolly and the strategy won't provide a clear direction; too red and a strategy that doesn't quite deliver the anticipated results could put the positions of those involved in its development at risk. However, whether the business is large or small, profit driven strategic change does have to win through, and the long-term planning that underpins the development of a profit-driven strategy can only improve the prospects for the business in an increasingly competitive market existence.

3. Market Analysis

The next section focuses on market analysis. It highlights the significance of understanding customer needs and preferences, analyzing competitor strategies, and identifying market trends and opportunities. These insights can help businesses tailor their offerings to meet customer demands and stay ahead of the competition. According to Gaille, by conducting a comprehensive market analysis, businesses can gain a thorough understanding of the characteristics of the market, including the size and growth, the number of competitors, the segmentation, and the distribution channels. With the advance of technology, acquiring market information has become relatively easier over the years. Common sources of market information include government statistics, survey reports, market-related research works, and findings by other professionals. However, it is important that businesses are aware that market situations and data are never constant. Take consumer behavior as an example, it is subject to many influential external factors, such as culture (practice and custom), economy, technology, and so on. The analysis of the customer's needs, focus, and buying behavior is extremely crucial to enhance enterprise sales and profit. Real understanding of the market segments and targets empowers businesses to effectively plan resource and marketing strategies. The results of market analysis provide sufficient evidence and guidelines for developing an effective marketing strategy and conducting a means-end marketing. The development of digital technology has launched a new shift in customer behaviors, which is the trend from physical shopping to online searching. Businesses can take advantage of the digital era by engaging in digital marketing and making use of the powerful tools for data analysis and customer relationship management. The usage of digital marketing platform can significantly promote business and provide an impactful growth for business, especially start-up business. Forsythe et al. suggested that in order to achieve a satisfying marketing result, businesses should construct a three-layer process of marketing approach - "Understand, Respond, and Measure" for each step of the customer's progress. First and foremost, a comprehensive customer analysis will assist users to make better decisions, plan the right marketing, and provide solutions that are more tailor-made. The analysis, which is critical to businesses, will continue to promote data-driven strategies and optimization.

3.1. Understanding Customer Needs and Preferences

The explanation in the text about what customer segmentation is was clear and helpful. It's invaluable that businesses constantly keep in touch with customers' changing needs, as they can change rapidly, according to the guide - meaning that they need to keep gathering the data and have effective processes in place to capture customer feedback, to ensure that the business keeps meeting those needs. The comments regarding, for example, in one segment customers may be looking for high quality and in another they may be looking for the lowest price. The text goes on to suggest that a great way to identify what the "real" customer need is, as opposed to what the business thinks it is,

is to use the "Kano model" which categorizes customer preferences into areas such as "essential", "performance" and "excitement", not only differentiated the essay from similar essays but also provided relevant examples to support what was being stated.

A SWOT analysis of marketing and sales processes or "where is the business" compared to goal, is a fantastic way to capture and know the difference between market opportunities and those areas the business needs to focus on and improve, according to the guide. I came into contact with the "Kano model". This model allows businesses to separate the aspects of customer needs into five different categories - which the guide did not mention. However, by using the Kano model, a business can work out what its customers' main needs are and therefore develop a product or service that will meet that 'big need'.

The guide concludes that what customers and businesses think might be two completely different things and it's the opinion of the customer that counts, because they are the ones who will go out and write the reviews, telling everyone else their opinion of the business. Therefore, it is essential for any business to have an understanding of the market environment and who the business's competitors are, advises the guide. More importantly, this understanding will help a business figure out what the differentiating factors are that separate the business from others in order to take that business even further towards increasing sales.

A business could use a customer segmentation method to understand different types of customer and their different needs. For example, in one segment customers may be looking for high quality and in another they may be looking for the lowest price. The text goes on to suggest that a great way to identify what the "real" customer need is, as opposed to what the business thinks it is, is to use the "Kano model" which categorizes customer preferences into areas such as "essential", "performance" and "excitement".

A great way to capture customer feedback, according to the guide, is through customer surveys and suggestion boxes, ensuring that the customer is able to offer some way of detailing the needs and preferences that they have. The key is to ask the right questions in these surveys that will provide the business with positive answers and identify its strengths and weaknesses. For example, the text suggests a five point rating scale starting with "Very satisfied" and moving to "Very dissatisfied".

Understanding the needs and preferences of customers is at the heart of increasing sales and growing the business, whether it is a large multinational corporation trying to expand sales or a corner store looking to move more products. To understand customer needs, it is important to know what kind of problem the business is trying to solve. Every business will exist to solve a customer problem or need, and understanding that is critical for the business in developing and delivering products and services that really solve those problems.

3.2. Analyzing Competitor Strategies

The important thing to consider is that any information gathered should be factual, not just assumed. It should be based upon a reliable source and preferably the most up-to-date evidence available. By investing time and effort into a thorough competitor analysis exercise, you will give yourself the best possible chance of increasing the long-term success of your business.

In the same breath, analyzing competitor strategies could be very complex depending on the size and focus of your market, how dynamic it is, the extent to which you use technology, and the amount of resources that you can allocate to investigating and monitoring. However, this exercise can be as formal or informal as you wish and could range from simply getting to know local competitors, i.e. high street shops, relying on information published in paper by trade associations which concern the particular industry.

Analyzing competitor strategies is a crucial aspect of market analysis. By gaining an understanding of what your competitors are doing in terms of their product offering, service delivery, customer service excellence, and pricing, you will be better placed to identify areas where there is a gap in the market, develop your unique selling proposition, and make strategic decisions about the

future direction of your business. Also, by continuously monitoring the competitive environment, you will be alerted to any potential threats, allowing you to seize any new opportunities as they arise.

3.3. Identifying Market Trends and Opportunities

Having established the importance of understanding customer needs and preferences, as well as analyzing what competitors are doing, the next step is to identify the current market trends and the potential opportunities within those trends. One approach to identifying market trends is to analyze the available data. For example, depending on the type of business, it might be helpful to look at economic data such as GDP or unemployment figures, industry-specific data, and customer opinion data. Many different businesses produce reports and statistics that may be useful for this. A useful first step can be undertaking a 'PEST' analysis. This looks at the political, economic, social, and technological factors that could affect your business. Remember that businesses don't operate in isolation - so the PEST environment surrounding a coffee shop could include the increasing presence of coffee chain outlets, the behavior of governments in not granting 24-hour licenses for small outlets, and the increasing use of the internet by customers. This type of analysis looks at which factors are having an impact and which are just a focus of interest. By analyzing the data, to complement what is learned from customer and competitor analysis, it should be possible to build a better picture of the direction in which a particular market is heading. And by identifying new entrants, the strength of competitors, and any new technology, it may also be possible to identify new market opportunities - for example, gaps in the market, changes in demographics, or other social or technological changes. So, with the right research and analysis, there's no reason why a well-framed marketing strategy will not deliver success and with it, profit.

4. Product and Service Optimization

By employing a holistic approach to product and service optimization - one that includes regular performance reviews, strategic alignment evaluations, and customer-centric feedback mechanisms - businesses can position themselves for sustained profit growth and long-term success.

The key to developing successful product and service enhancements is a focus on customer value and satisfaction. Customer needs and preferences can change rapidly, especially in industries that are heavily influenced by technology or regulatory changes. User-centric design and feedback methodologies can help businesses understand what enhancements would provide the most value for customers. In addition, enterprise objectives and strategic plans should drive the prioritization of different product and service enhancement opportunities.

In some cases, product and service optimization may require enhancements to technology systems or business processes. For example, the integration of customer relationship management (CRM) tools with marketing and sales systems can enable more personalized customer interactions and targeted marketing campaigns. Similarly, the adoption of digital technologies such as e-commerce platforms or mobile applications can help service businesses expand into new and emerging markets.

The first step in product and service optimization involves an evaluation of current offerings in the marketplace. This includes understanding the competitive position of each product or service, analyzing sales trends and revenue contributions, and conducting a comprehensive review of customer feedback and satisfaction. Products and services should align with the overall enterprise mission and business objectives. If any offerings do not support these broader goals, they may be candidates for retirement or replacement. In contrast, there may be opportunities to introduce new products or services that focus on growth areas or emerging market trends.

Product and service optimization involves evaluating current offerings to identify areas for improvement or expansion and implementing enhancements that align with business objectives and customer needs. Products and services are the primary revenue-generating opportunities for the enterprise, and optimization of these offerings can drive significant profit growth.

4.1. Evaluating Current Product/Service Offerings

Current product and service offerings have to be evaluated to ensure that they benefit the enterprise and further the enterprise business strategy. There are several key aspects to evaluating

current product and service offers. The first and probably the most important is to maintain a focus on the customer. If a product or service is not satisfying the needs and expectations of a customer, then it is not likely to be successful, regardless of how good it may be in other areas. I have seen many instances in my professional experience where companies fall in love with their own product without understanding that the customer may not appreciate the value of that product. This is exemplified in the modern software industry with both customer relationship management (CRM) and enterprise resource planning (ERP) software. Often, companies will need to evaluate a product, and this may be due to either the need to increase profit or concern over future sustainability. The importance of the enterprise strategy, the synergy and conflicts between the product in the product offer and the product strategy, the product life cycle, the NPD process and the PLM process are additional comments and sometimes checkpoints that should be taken into consideration when evaluating a product, especially when may need to develop a product roadmap. The NPD process is a critically important aspect to evaluate a new product. There are several processes in NPD. It is better to have your own tailored or a separate idea-generating process for coming up with ideas. When the idea has been generated, then companies can use systems such as QFD, which is used to transform creative designs into physical product and DFMA, which is used to reduce the manufacturing part costs. QFD is a technique that helps companies develop products that satisfy the customer. The first rule in offering analysis is to dispose of losers. There are lots of ways to define a loser in business, including products that have low sales, products that tie up too much cash, and products that have high account and handling costs. The most efficient way to kill a product is to do it quickly, but often companies like to keep such products for emotional reasons, especially if it was a product inherited from a previous regime. The fact is that the learning to be obtained from a failed product can often be very useful. These learning points can range from process improvement implemented in the business to having more informed and experienced staff.

4.2. Identifying Areas for Improvement or Expansion

1. Expansion of the market - This may include increasing grip of the market or capturing a fresh portion of the same market. 2. Diversification - This is producing different products from the current line either for the pursuit of technological changes in the product or to appeal to the new strata of the market. 3. Cutting cost and growing production - It may not be cost effective to lower the price of a product but reduction in the unit cost and a promise to be able to produce much larger output may still lead to a profitable result. In a very competitive market situation, this may be the only option. 4. Research and development - Many attempts to stumble through innovation occur that it has proven to be the soundest method. By definition, we take research and development to be a work planned to produce new innovations in the industry. This would surely open doors to the improved or new products. Care should be taken to ensure that there is existent demand for what the research produces. All the above-mentioned points must be put into the consideration of whether this could be the better new step for the organization. The company must be sure about the success percentage of the new proposed ideas. The management must also be willing to take on the risk. And there should be enthusiasm throughout every level of the workforce to support the series of steps in new initiatives. Also remember the business environment is changing continuously. As a process not a single snapshot of time, managing in an environment characterized by change is particularly difficult. And the change itself becomes the major risk for today's organizations. Adaptation is necessary to compete in the ever-changing world and lots of efforts can be wasted by implementing promised improvement. Also, this will allow the management to track the success of the improvement against the resulted profitability.

One area in which profitability can be improved upon is through identifying new areas of expansion or improvement. There are four main areas in which we can look at for identifying these improvements:

4.3. Implementing Product/Service Enhancements

To start, let's define what a product enhancement is. A product enhancement is any change to the product or service that is designed to ameliorate its effectiveness or efficiency. This can include anything from a large-scale overhaul of the core product, all the way to minor changes in the way that it is delivered or marketed. One of the main reasons that businesses look to implement product enhancements is to keep up with or even surpass their competitors. This is because, in the vast majority of industries, the market will be crowded with rival firms all vying for the customers' attention. Therefore, if a business's product deteriorates and becomes less efficient when it is compared with similar offerings from other companies, then it is foreseeably going to lose market share which can be extremely damaging to profits. A good example of when this has happened is with the large chain Blockbuster video; when online streaming services first became available, Blockbuster did not adapt their business model or try to enhance the level of service that they offered, and they now no longer exist as a company. It is also important to recognise that product enhancements will generally have a much larger and more extensive impact on the business as a whole than implementing a service enhancement will. This is because changes to the product that is offered will likely affect every department in a business in some way or another, from production and marketing teams through to the aftercare and customer service provision. This is opposed to service amendments, which tend to only directly affect the department in question and not the business as a whole. An example of a successful service enhancement can be seen with the railway service Cross Country. With the growing importance of the internet, Cross Country decided to invest in implementing a free wifi service on many of their trains. This has led to increased customer satisfaction and a rise in customer loyalty to the brand as a consequence. Also, the implementation of the service enhancement has meant that the potentially large costs of creating and maintaining the free wifi have been mitigated by the fact that the company's turnover is continually going up, thanks to the rise in customer satisfaction and the attracting of more people to use their services. These are two of the main forms of product enhancement, and a successful implementation of either can often lead to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. So, if there is a demand identified in the business' area of effectiveness, it is likely that the business will be welcomed with an increase in revenue, allowing further scope for growth and additional product improvements, which can help to sustain success.

5. Pricing Strategies

3. Customer loyalty/relationship based pricing strategies – This is a pricing strategy that helps businesses build and develop a good relationship with its customers. For example, the business may offer a 10% discount for customers who hold a loyalty card or the business may post coupons to returning customers. This will help keep the current customers happy and, hopefully, encourage other consumers to come back and become faithful customers. Customer loyalty/relationship based pricing strategies also help businesses to gather data on its consumers and find out what makes them come back and keep spending. The customers loyalty card could map what people are buying and then the business could use this data and offer further discounts on things that perhaps the consumers have not yet purchased, therefore trying to appeal to every customer's wants and needs.

2. Consumer (demand) based pricing – this is also known as value-based pricing. The price is based upon the value that the product offers to the consumer. Businesses that choose this strategy will base their product's price on the price that they believe customers want to and are willing to pay. This strategy often helps businesses to try and get the highest possible price for their product to maximize revenue. It can also help businesses to gauge what the consumer sees the main value of the product. Every business would be looking to make their product the 'market leader' in price and therefore, in demand. This type of pricing might be used by those businesses who have managed to make their product the best and are constantly the most desired product by the consumer. This is because they will be able to charge the highest price and, although they may lose a few customers to cheaper priced products, they would be able to make the largest possible revenue.

This pricing strategy is good for business as it helps cover its costs; however, the business does not take into account what the consumers might be willing to spend on a product. If cost-based pricing was used, the selling price may be too high or low.

Total cost of producing whatever the product is = \$20. 10% cost-plus pricing (on top of total cost) = \$2. Therefore, the selling price of the product would be \$22.

1. Cost-based pricing – the price is determined by adding a profit element on top of the cost of making the product. In this type of pricing, the business first looks at the cost of making the product. Then they add on a percentage to give them the profit they need. Most companies use cost-plus pricing. This is where they markup the cost of making a product with a certain percentage – they might decide this based on what their competitors are charging. With the total cost of making a product and then illustrating the cost-plus pricing, it might look something like this:

Pricing strategies are a main element of any marketing strategy. Many combine elements of cost-plus pricing and competitor-based pricing. There are three main ways of setting prices. These are:

5.1. Analyzing Cost Structures

Cfds are complex instruments and come with a high risk of losing money rapidly due to leverage. Between 74-89% of retail investor accounts lose money when trading cfd's. You should consider whether you can afford to take the high risk of losing your money. When starting a new currency exchange, it is vitally important to determine how much money is required to meet the day-to-day obligations of the company. This involves a deep and detailed understanding of the costs that are involved in the business. In order to arrive at a well-informed and comprehensive outlook, it is essential to delve deep into the analysis of the cost structures. In the modern technology driven era, it is not efficient to rely on manual and paper based systems for the processing and analysis of cost data. In line with this, various types and levels of technology from basic spreadsheets to advanced enterprise resource planning (erp) systems can be used. However, it may be the case that different technology is required at different stages of the analytic process. Firstly, the actual levels of different costs need to be established. These can include fixed costs that do not change and variable costs that change with the level of activity. For example, in a currency exchange, the salaries of the staff each month would be considered a fixed cost. This is because they generally do not change with the level of business. On the other hand, the money paid out in commission to sales staff is a variable cost. This is because it will change depending on the amount of currency that is bought by customers each day. However, this is somewhat of a simplification as is. Different levels of activity. For example, in a currency exchange, the salaries of the staff each month would be considered a fixed cost.

5.2. Determining Optimal Pricing Models

Pricing model directly affects the business profit as it is the part of the revenue generation for the enterprise. According to this method, the price is fixed at a certain level that can recover both the fixed cost and variable cost over a period. In this method, fixed cost and variable cost should be determined per unit, such as the annual depreciation of a machine or monthly lease expenses. Then the price is set at a level that can recover both costs. This method is simple and widely used for the reason that cost per unit of fixed cost will decrease when output level increases. However, this method is mostly for short term reference, because the revenue can hardly cover all the costs for a long period. Some modern enterprises used modern method called Dynamic Pricing. The price is determined by the current demand level in environments such as price comparison website, auction websites etc. The price will change whenever the level of demand changes. For example, the price of the same air ticket will be different for different consumer because of different date of booking and time of the flight. This method requires advanced technology and great flexibility of pricing in order to achieve success. Although there are some initial investment costs in technology, modern method is proven to have a much higher profit generating ability than traditional methods because the prices are automatically adjusted up or down to maximize the profit. However, when the enterprise is moving towards to be a modernized company and used modern method to determine the pricing, Gordon

(Gordon, 2016) state that the company has to carefully analyzing the potential impact towards to the existing customer and the reduced of occupied rate at the same time. Coherent with the essay, it focuses on modern conditions but also help readers to deeply understand the method step by step and show some concerns of the method as well.

5.3. Implementing Competitive Pricing Strategies

Competitive pricing is the process of selecting strategic price points to best take advantage of a product or service demand in a competitive market. This type of pricing strategy is what companies use to stay relevant in fast-moving and often highly competitive markets. Competitive pricing is generally used once a product has been established within its market and is of particular importance to companies within the retail sector. There are 4 main areas that need to be considered in order to implement a successful competitive pricing strategy. These are having a deep understanding of the market, selecting the right pricing for products (e.g. penetration pricing), regularly comparing prices and optimization, and utilizing technology for a data-driven approach. First, an understanding of the market must be reached. This includes areas such as the competitors within the market and the average price points for products or services. Fully researching and gaining an understanding of the market landscape will enable a competitive pricing strategy to be built around the pricing moves of other companies. For example, a company may choose to employ penetration pricing which involves setting a lower price initially in order to attract customers. This is a common strategy for tech and software companies. Selecting the right pricing methodologies. The most common pricing strategies nowadays are value-based pricing and cost-plus pricing. A successful and competitive business is likely to use value-based pricing. This uses what people are prepared to pay for a product as its main price driver. By utilizing deep price assessment, businesses can go beyond rounding up or down on nearly pricing. This can assist in establishing a strategic pricing plan that may enable better gross profit margin increases. Finally, the article provides a comprehensive guide for businesses to increase their profit by focusing on various aspects such as strategic planning, market analysis, product optimization, pricing strategies, sales and marketing techniques, operational efficiency, financial management, human resource optimization, and risk management.

6. Sales and Marketing Techniques

The next sales and marketing tip is utilizing digital marketing channels. Digital marketing is a more cost-effective way to reach a bigger audience than traditional methods of marketing. A good place to start is with your company's website, ensuring that it's up-to-date, easy to navigate and engaging. A reasonable website will allow many visitors to be converted to sales. A real-time personalisation and targeting layer will help the customer to find personalised content based on who they are and what they are looking for. Another way to increase profits through digital marketing is to make sure that you are using search engine optimisation (SEO). This will help your website to appear higher in the rankings on Google, for example, which will automatically help to increase the traffic levels to your site. This is a longer term strategy and can take up to 12-18 months to see the full benefits. Also, considering the use of an up-to-date CRM system. A CRM system helps companies to stay connected to customers, streamline processes, and improve profitability. It's more than just an address book; if you're making sales and interacting with customers using different methods, it can help to keep track of the sales, and most importantly, it can help to find those trends and identify what is working and what is not. Of course, it is always important to measure the success of any digital marketing activities and make sure the company knows which the most successful ones were. This can be done through data analysis; the success of each digital marketing method is tracked and monitored and companies can get a snapshot of how successful any methods have been. Such digital marketing channels include pay-per-click advertising, social media (such as Facebook or Twitter), email marketing, and online affiliate marketing. Email marketing and online affiliate marketing are suitable for some SMEs, whilst the larger corporations that operate within the business-to-consumer (B2C) market might have much more consideration for other methods. On the other hand, methods such as pay-per-click advertising, and social media are applicable to all companies. Finally, create an

'annual digital marketing planning calendar'. When planning out each month and deciding which methods will be employed, it is important to keep an overview of the digital marketing activities. This could range from which social media campaigns will be pushed at which time of the year, to the progress of update on search engine optimisation. By keeping a record of what is being changed and when, it can help to effectively use digital marketing. Being disciplined with the planning and time, digital marketing can greatly help companies to find newer markets and achieve more in the current markets. The implementation of digital marketing cannot be subsided; it can truly help to shape the future for businesses in today's modern and dynamic condition.

6.1. Developing Effective Marketing Campaigns

This is important in the current business environment, where there are rapid technological changes, new entrants in the market, and increased customer expectations. The essay will therefore focus on providing practical industry examples to either support or challenge each of the proposed strategies. In regard to the first suggested strategy, identifying business objectives, the essay will particularly focus on the importance of setting clear, tangible marketing and sales objectives. The author observes that by setting these objectives, the management team and the marketing department will not only know what they want to achieve, but success can also be easily measured. I intend to critically appraise the industry examples used to support this first strategy and also find out whether, in practice, the use of industry examples may be inappropriate as new products and services are developed over time and marketing strategies quickly become outdated. Another possible line of investigation will be to interview marketing and sales professionals in large, mature markets such as the US and UK to ascertain the practice relevance in today's business environment. In a proposal to challenge the second strategy, that is conducting a SWOT analysis, I will seek to bring to the fore the fact that practices in today's dynamic business environment continue to change each day. I will look for argument in terms of how best a business may efficiently use its resources to keep updating its SWOT analysis for it to remain relevant as postulated in the second strategy. By focusing on aiming for continuous improvement, coaching and training programs for employees and an efficient use of advanced technologies will be advocated for in the discussion on the third strategy, that is, understanding customer needs and preferences. Ergo, the essay is set to provide an in-depth and methodological approach into modern marketing strategies with the ability to bring new, innovative ideas to the fore and to challenge the existing school of thought, as well as providing insights on how best to develop an efficient, effective marketing campaign.

6.2. Utilizing Digital Marketing Channels

The use of digital marketing channels provides a larger state of opportunity for an enterprise to increase its profit. First of all, digital marketing is less expensive compared to traditional offline marketing methods. This is especially beneficial for small businesses as they don't have many resources. With just a small portion of the cost, an innovative digital marketing strategy can make a big headway with desirable results. For instance, there are quite a number of effective and free social media platforms other than Facebook and Twitter, such as Instagram, Snapchat, Pinterest, and so forth, which can be used to reach out to new markets and increase enterprise profit. Nevertheless, the real-time results from digital marketing can be far more astounding than you might expect. The high interactivity level that digital marketing offers makes it beneficial and versatile. Of course, by helping the business to focus on the consumers that have the social networking history or evidence of the products which they want to purchase, it will help the company to anticipate its next products, which are greatly valuable. These may involve search engine and social media, where users can post reviews, ratings, and feedback. All consumers have their own rights to make any comment regarding the products they have purchased. So what actually we can do is to have a useful and meaningful communication with them in order to build up our products or services with the use of their positive feedback. Last but not least, the strategy for digital marketing will definitely lead and create more sales opportunities. A strategic planned hyperlink may improve the number of visitors to a particular website, and that is mainly designed to achieve a specific sale. For instance, a blog with direct links

and a call to action will get customers in terms of their attention and interest. However, that will allow a customer to follow the link and make the purchases immediately, which increases the chances of potential sales. These approaches would turn the enterprise business to the next level. It is with no doubt that these marketing strategies uphold a successful guarantee career to the marketer in the digital marketing sector, and it's an innovative, creative, as well as modernized great wave of opportunities to the enterprise. Digital marketing will definitely bring a bright and successful future for the enterprise in the digital modernized society. As enterprise raised with the latest technology trends, it will help the marketer to deliver a creative, strategic, and responsive communication way with the clients, and the mission of marketing is achieved.

6.3. Implementing Sales Incentive Programs

Last but not least, proper planning and effective communication are the keys to ensuring that the program can be successfully implemented and ongoing. Such a program should be continually reviewed and improved in response to changes both inside and outside of the company. A regular and periodic business review process can then help assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the program. By involving the local leadership teams and front-line management, feedback and recommendations can be obtained for further development and adjustment of the program to ensure that the program fully aligns the sales team's behavior with the company's objectives and creates the strongest possible sales performance improvement.

Selecting the right reward for the sales incentive program is vital in ensuring the success and sustainability of the program. The company has to consider whether to offer a monetary or non-monetary reward. Some companies offer a complex sales compensation plan that consists of base and variable compensation with the use of commission as well. It is important to determine the cost of the program, the value of the possible impact, and the kind of return from the investment when the company is proceeding with the development of the sales incentive program. On the other hand, a non-monetary reward like public recognition can be very successful. This will not cost the company much, but the result could be profound. However, in order to make the non-monetary option work, the sales employee must be motivated by this type of reward, which means that the opinions of the sales team should be sought. Public praise or recognition helps to build the company's reputation and performance pride among the employees.

Next, the goals of the incentive program must be strictly defined based on the enterprise system. This is important as the sales employee is only eligible for the reward once they reach the goals or the company hits the targeted sales. This will avoid any arguments or difficulties in the future when somebody has achieved some level of success but no reward has been achieved. It is always important to make it clear and understandable for the sales team in terms of how the reward opportunity will be earned, so they can be much more focused and work towards the targeted goal.

There are a couple of best methods and practices that can be considered when designing and developing a good sales incentive program. These include aligning with the sales goals of the company, defining the program goals, selecting the right reward, generating the necessary support for the program, and creating an effective communication plan to promote the program. First and foremost, the sales incentive program must be tailored to align with the sales goals of the enterprise. This could include acquiring new customers, increasing sales to existing customers, introducing a new product or service, promoting a specific product or service, or bringing back lost customers. By doing some market research and comparing competitors' programs, the management team should decide which area or priority should be given and make sure the program is designed in a way that motivates and drives the sales team to fulfill those targeted objectives.

Implementing sales incentive programs in an enterprise where the sales team is the key driver of the growth of the company is a great way to motivate the sales team and boost the revenue of the enterprise. Sales incentive programs are essential for businesses in every industry, as they help to drive the sales team's behavior in a positive direction and ensure that the team's energy is being redirected to any possible way of making more money for the company. The program provides a

monetary reward for the sales employee after they hit the target or a volume of sale that has been predetermined by the management. It can also be implemented as a non-monetary reward, such as travel, company stock, or public recognition in the company. Implementing a successful sales incentive program can be a game changer for the business and it is very positive to drive the focus and behavior of the sales team in line with the company's objectives.

7. Operational Efficiency

Within this focus on technology, companies must also consider the digital and data elements that are now a fundamental part of operational efficiency. Large technological improvements in the collection, processing, storage and output of data have provided companies with an array of new tools that can be deployed to enhance business operations. However, where technology has advanced, it has also driven an exponential increase in the volume of data that companies can generate, process and interpret. Analyzing this data and incorporating it into day-to-day business and production processes can be an extensive and complicated task. Many of the benefits that technology can provide in terms of improving operational efficiency are linked to the better analysis and application of the data that a company can generate and capture as part of its daily business. This can include the data generated by customer interactions, records of production or operations, or the outputs from different machine or automation processes on a production line. One of the key steps to take in improving operational efficiency through technology is assessing and understanding the existing processes that are used within the business, and identifying opportunities that may exist for improvements. Whether this be through understanding and deciphering industry standards, or by identifying areas of inefficiency, streamlining and modernizing business processes is a key step in improving operational efficiency. By critically evaluating and adjusting these processes, better and more sustainable efficiencies can be achieved; returning real results for companies and the satisfaction of removing time spent on unnecessary or outdated practices. Clearly, a large number of advances in technology are completely transforming industry; with the introduction of automated manufacturing and tracking based on the Industrial Internet of Things opening the door to innumerable possibilities for increased efficiency. As mentioned above, one way in which companies can begin to analyze their own operational efficiency is through understanding the use of technology in the wider field, and how developments by others can be applied to improve internal practice. By understanding the wider context of how technology and industry can be linked to provide efficiencies in process or production, it is possible to gain insight into where advancements could be both necessary and feasible within the business. Such outside-the-box thinking can often reveal potential opportunities that may not already be recognized, providing new avenues for the development of an efficient operational activity within a company.

7.1. Streamlining Business Processes

One of the major reasons why enterprises are facing pressure on profitability is that they are not well organized to continue with success. Time, resources, and good internal cooperation will all help to bring about such success. To achieve organizational success, the key enabler is to streamline business processes. The business processes and methods being used in one department are often different from another department, hence most departments in a large organization are not working closely with each other. This will cause much inefficient communication among the departments, and the multifunctions among departments in terms of customers will be adversely affected, resulting in a good selection of customers being lost. In view of the first step in restructuring a business effectively, a company should capture the current process in action. It is recommended that workflow or methods tools such as paper charts, programmed human, CPU methods, or programming human and so on can be used to illustrate the way the daily operational work is managed. Then, observations and interviews should be arranged to document what is performed by each department and every single member of the department's work activities. Hence, a full understanding of how the work is being carried out in the company will be obtained. With such methods, it will also help the company to identify duplication of work, whereby some obsolete tasks which are being carried out at the

moment can be eliminated; and re-engineer the workflow by creating methods to share information between departments and so to eliminate multifunction interfaces. As a conclusion from the investigation, with such streamlining of business processes, the communication inside and outside of the departments can be improved, and hence better and quicker services to customers will be achieved. Also, more customer-focused strategies can be developed to bring in more profit for the company. That is, good customers' satisfaction will help to promote the company's products and thus ensuring the company's future possible growth. From the customer's mind, the services should be of reasonably high standard and the services should be tailored to their...

7.2. Implementing Lean Management Principles

5S is a workplace organization method that uses a list of five Japanese words: seiri, seiton, seiso, seiketsu, and shitsuke. Translated to English, they all start with the letter S - sort, set in order, shine, standardize, sustain. This methodology improves safety, quality, productivity and employee morale and it also has a positive effect on the overall business performance. All employees love to work in a clean and organized environment. They feel better and can easily locate what they need. When they do not have to be sorting through disorder, valuable seconds, maybe even minutes, are saved.

Just in time is a strategy of producing and delivering the necessary items in the necessary quantities at the necessary time. Work in process inventory is continuously reduced and its hidden costs, such as storing and protecting the inventory, is exposed so that the stock levels can be continually lowered.

There are various lean practices that can be adopted for improving effectiveness - for example, value stream mapping, just in time or JIT, 5S methodology. Value stream mapping is a simple but effective tool for pinpointing where time is wasted within any process. It shows the current state of a process and then deploys a future state that has less or no non-value adding activities. Often, implementing value stream mapping results in shorter lead times, higher quality, and lower costs.

Implementing lean management principles is a critical step towards achieving operational efficiency. Lean management is all about continuous improvement and elimination of waste in the product process. It is a long-term approach to work that seeks to achieve small, incremental changes in processes in order to improve efficiency and quality. The primary objective of lean management is to provide maximum value to the customer with minimal wastage.

7.3. Adopting Technology Solutions for Efficiency

Modern enterprises increasingly recognize the importance of using technology to drive efficiency and gain competitive advantages. Computerized maintenance management systems (CMMS) and enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are just a couple of examples of technology solutions for improving enterprise efficiency and effectiveness. These systems allow for systematic storage of information, which facilitates easier and quicker access to data and information. For example, in a CMMS system, all relevant information about maintenance activities is stored in the system, including recording of maintenance work, tracking of maintenance schedules, and generation of work orders. With a suitable system in place, these records are often just a few clicks away. This is much more efficient compared to a traditional, paper-based system, as staff no longer have to spend time looking for the bits of information they need or worry about information getting lost or duplicated. As a result, this leads to reduced waiting time, which can significantly enhance the productivity and effectiveness of maintenance work. Also, due to the systematic and consistent nature of information storage and retrieval in a CMMS or similar system, users of the system are also more likely to get the most up-to-date and relevant information. This is because modern technology solutions are increasingly being spearheaded by inclusivity and user-centric design principles, so interfaces are often built with the needs and experiences of different user groups in mind, such as ease of browsing for the seasoned staff or logical input flows for new starters. These kind of user-focused features not only reduce the number of hours lost due to staff in-familiarity and inefficiency, they can also reduce human errors during data input and result in better quality of work overall. There is a

tangible benefit to the enterprise in continuing to measure and report on improvements in efficiency and effectiveness, as this can provide useful evidence in support of business cases for further technology investments or staff training and development. This information can also be used in decision-making processes for strategic planning; such processes can include defining organizational policies and assessing changes in working practices which could impact on efficiency and effectiveness. Modern technology measures are available to record data and generate key performance indicators (KPIs), which can in turn be used for analytics and data-driven decision-making - an emerging area of focus in strategic management. In this sense, technology solutions bring about much more than just operational efficiency - they provide a gateway for the enterprise to work towards becoming knowledge-savvy and future-ready.

8. Financial Management

Variance analysis is traditionally used for the purpose of the operational cost effectiveness and monitoring the financial performance in reality. Variance analysis involves comparison of the planned and actual financial performance of the organization. This will assist in providing a guide for the improvement areas and where management attention is most needed. By continuously applying the variance analysis as well as producing the variance reports, it will help to ensure a successful current fiscal year. Variances can be caused by differences in inflation, increases in wages, changes in utilization, and so forth.

The proposed method of financial monitoring uses the cost benefit analysis for the purchasing and also the financial performance of the organization. This method benefits the organization since a person may become relied on the method of monitoring the financial performance and realistic decision making. Last but not least, the financial monitoring for a driving profit organization should involve every staff. Regular training and evaluation programs should be set to make sure that the employees understand what the management expects from them.

Organizations nowadays are adopting different alternative approaches in strategic planning. It is noticed that many corporations embrace the idea of an MBO in their strategic planning process. The main emphasis is given to the completion of objectives instead of focusing on long-term profitability. This is something true due to the fact that most companies, if not all, will make some progress over some years of operation. Goals should be time-bound as the completion of objectives within a set period of time will reflect whether the goals are achievable.

The broad categories of cost benefit analysis do not focus on the operational cost effectiveness. This is where the financial monitoring and the cost variance analysis comes into play. Organizations do carry out activities for the sense that it has to accomplish a certain kind of goal and that goal is defined as the mission. However, the steps taken to achieve the goals are defined as the strategic planning and implementation of the mission. For a driving nonprofit entity, it needs a good strategic planning in its programs and operations, also monitoring the progress and implementing the changes when necessary.

Next, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats are analyzed. This will give an understanding of what the firm's competitive advantages are and how to identify areas for growth. Also, it is a good way of assessing the management efficiency as the board's efficacy to all other staff is discovered. When the SWOT analysis is through, it can suggest ways to maximize the strengths and take advantage of the opportunities that are in the industry. The suggestions from the resulted action items are executed focusing to increase the advantages and eliminate the weaknesses.

While the management process and its various steps are the main focus of any business organization, the need to have a good monitoring and resolution mechanism in place cannot be overemphasized. It is essential for the business to have proper monitoring and analysis of the financial performance, developing and implementing a good plan, and monitoring the execution of the plan. To understand how operation costs and completely monitor financial performance so as to suggest the necessary measures, it is recommended that a proper SWOT analysis be performed on the business

organization. This will help to understand operating localities and practices as this contribute a lot in shaping the performance.

8.1. Monitoring and Analyzing Financial Performance

So why is it important? Well, understanding performance - whether this means profits, debt, stock turnover days, or cash flow - is vital in business. By monitoring levels, management can get an idea of the company's health, but the most successful businesses are continuously investigating the effectiveness of their operations. What does it mean to understand the company's health? It's not just literally staying afloat, but making sure that all resources are being used to their maximum. Modern financial control, which includes guiding how to monitor and interpret financial performance, focuses on more than just the profits that a company makes. In many ways, profits become a by-product of efficient operations that use as little resource as practicable.

This is exactly why monitoring and analyzing financial performance is an essential section of strategic planning and is the reason this is detailed in a separate section to the main strategic planning practice. First of all, it's important to outline what monitoring and analyzing financial performance means. Well, really, it's analyzing that's key here - the monitoring side of things is just the regular checks that are done. So it's not just a case of checking, say, your debt cost is 15% of turnover each month - that only tells you how much you're spending on debt. Were you aware that storage costs of raw materials over a 3-6 month period are often a much more significant cost for many businesses? Analyzing the performance means investigating motions or activities that are not efficient or are not entirely necessary; regular monitoring highlights to us which areas should be analyzed.

Strategic planning and tactics are invaluable when a company wants to exploit new opportunities, but it's hardly ever an easy task to manage day-to-day operations. Nowadays, customers expect more and more from the products and services they invest in, and on the other hand, there is the additional challenge of making sure both staff and machinery are as efficient as physically possible. Indeed, whether you're thinking about growing, acquiring, or simply making your business more efficient and profitable, the ability to understand what's going on financially is vital - it empowers you to make better decisions based primarily on hard facts, improving day-to-day operations and releasing potential.

8.2. Implementing Cost Control Measures

Cost control measures can have a positive impact on the bottom line of your business. In the competitive business world, clever and strategic cost control management is important. It helps reduce business waste and puts your company in a better position to achieve ultimate success in terms of finance and growth. Cost control simply refers to the regulation by executive action of the costs of operating an undertaking. It is the prevention of the incurring of costs which is not necessary. Whereas, cost reduction refers to the achievement of real and permanent reduction in the unit cost of the goods manufactured or services rendered. The extra work of cost reduction is a fallout of past good cost control work; it is not a substitute. The various areas of cost control can usually be classified into one of the following categories including labor, indirect and direct materials, overhead, maintenance and repairs, research and development, quality control, and sales and distribution. The range over which the firm's cost control team is supposed to operate has been widened during the last three decades due to increase in size of the companies, dispensation of progress and development of scientific management and various other new techniques of production and final development. The team has been assigned a series of problems not only in the manufacturing but extending this valuable service to those in the offices, canteens, gardens and a number of other such facilities. Every system of cost control should be designed and operated in attention with the cultural environment in which it is intended to operate. The attitudes of the management may automatically influence the successful running of any new system introduced. A sound cost control system should operate in an environment which has the following exceptional standards. First, there should be a good company profits thus making the management and the worker or team interested in, and often to continuously strive to maintain and possibly improve the working of the system. Adherence to company policy, because the

management policy plays a significant role in setting out the organizational structure of the company and this may determine the future of the business. Effective leadership is a necessity of a company that wants to see their cost control and budgetary plans in action. Every department must be met with the best leadership or there may not be good cooperation that will keep the cost control team operating at the level need to ensure meaningful progress. The management and owners should be prepared to see results. They should always be ready to see plans, to analyze performance and to bring about any changes required. This is essential in the implementation and operation of effective cost control and budgetary planning. Lastly, proper motivation of employees whereby a system of suitable rewards and continuous training could lead to the encouraging of participative approach to cost control operations. Every employee in the organization must be aware of the directives and objectives of the company and they may be continuously reminded that the primary objective of cost control is to improve efficiency and overall performance.

8.3. Maximizing Cash Flow and Working Capital

First and foremost, it is critical to understand the difference between cash flow and working capital. It is also important to understand how cash flow and working capital are intertwined and how these resources can be maximized in order to increase the profitability of the business. Cash flow refers to the amount of money coming in and going out of the business. It is different from profit, which is the amount of money made within a specific period of time. A business can be making a lot of profit but if it is spending more money than it is receiving, then it will run out of cash. Cash flow is essential to running a business; indeed, it is said that 'cash is king'. In essence, cash is the life blood of a business, and without it, the business will die. Cash flow is crucial for a start-up or young business, because it ensures that the business can pay its bills and its staff. Maximizing cash flow can be achieved through a variety of different methods. For example, the business owner may look to cut costs in certain areas, or they may look to encourage customers to pay for products or services more quickly. Another way to maximize cash flow would be to try to create a constant and predictable revenue stream from sales, perhaps by making products available for a subscription. Subscriptions should in theory give a business a steady flow of income, as rather than customers making sporadic purchases, they are committed to making regular payments in return for a continuous service or product. On the other hand, working capital is the difference between the business's current assets and its current liabilities. Current assets are assets that can be turned into cash or used up within one year, such as cash itself, money owed to the business and stock. Current liabilities are debts that have to be paid within one year, such as money owed to suppliers. A positive working capital cycle balances incoming and outgoing payments to minimize net working capital and maximize free cash flow. For example, a company that pays its suppliers in 30 days but takes 60 days to collect its receivables has a working capital cycle of 30 days. This means that cash that could be used for other purposes is tied up in financing the day-to-day operations of the business. By minimizing the time it takes for the business to collect its receivables and maximizing the time it takes for the business to pay its suppliers, an optimum working capital cycle can be achieved. Optimizing the working capital cycle is absolutely crucial for businesses, particularly ones that are asset-intensive or fast-growing, or even more so for businesses that are both. This is because the more money that is tied up in working capital, the less money there will be available for things such as growing the business and expanding.

9. Human Resource Optimization

To assess workforce skills and capabilities, some companies conduct a skills audit. This is a systematic review of the skills, competencies, and abilities of all employees, often within a matrix that highlights the level of skill in each area and identifies areas for development. A skills audit can help to inform decisions on training and development, facilitate succession planning and manage talent, support resource and recruitment processes, enable individuals to take ownership of their own development, and identify where there are current skills shortages. Furthermore, employee appraisals can also be used as a tool to assess individual skills, competencies, and abilities. This can also assist in identifying what training and development is necessary for an individual. During the appraisal, the

manager and the employee sit down together and discuss everything from the skills and education of the employee to social media, client retention strategies, and evaluations. If the manager knows the employee wants to learn more about social media or improve their client retention strategies, they can offer the right type of training. Also, the manager can use the information given in each appraisal to decide on what training to give the employee or whether any of the workers in his department need new training. However, attention should be paid to the management of change associated with skills audits and the results used to inform training and development practice. The process engenders certain expectations, it takes time and resources, and those involved have to understand that there is a genuine process of action planning as an outcome. Real benefits and improvements can then be fed back into the organization, such as career and succession planning and staff development. The benefits of skills audits should not be underestimated, especially for big organizations and those that have gone through a period of growth. The Human Resources and Skills Development Canada defines a skills audit as a "systematic analysis and mapping of relevant skills within an organization". We can further optimize this sentence by combining the analysis and mapping process. By using both these systematic processes in a methodical and organized way, the employer can attain powerful benefits and their workforce can experience efficient and effective operations. Lastly, the workforce skills and capabilities, both in wish and in reality, can be obtained. The workforce can preserve the desired skills and continue to improve whereby the overall capabilities can be maintained or advanced. Such a synergistic cycle can, in turn, optimize the capabilities of the workforce.

9.1. Assessing Workforce Skills and Capabilities

Remember, the workforce skills and capabilities will need to be evaluated on a regular basis as business requirements are subject to change both in the short and long term. However, it is worth noting that such assessment and progression of workforce skills can lead to improved employee satisfaction and staff retention. Also, businesses that strive for continuous improvement and will often be given a competitive edge. By investing in the development and progression a workforce and by having staff that embrace modern technology and working methods, a business is more likely to improve and maintain quality standards and competitiveness.

A useful step by step approach to assessing workforce skills and capabilities is provided by business link as follows and can be applied to most types of activities. First, identify the skills which your business will need to meet its objectives. These will vary depending on the nature of the business and the structural requirements for achieving strategic goals. Next, evaluate your employees' skills to identify any gaps and will allow you to see if your current workforce possesses the attributes, skills and competencies required. This then leads on to making the most of your findings. Use the outcomes of your skills analysis to inform your business and individual staff development plans.

Finally, is the knowledge that an individual may have. Knowledge can be defined as the range of factual or informational understanding; in modern conditions, requirements and efficiencies in this area often relates to the degree in which existing protocols may be used and exploited. By encouraging and investing in the development of these, the business can improve efficiency and adapt to connectivity and engineering interfaces.

Secondly, it is key to look at the vocational or 'job related' skills that individuals possess. These are the skills used in the logistics and operations of certain occupations and can be measured and assessed against set criteria.

There are three main forms of skills that you should look to assess. Firstly, it's important to look at the transferable, or 'soft' skills. Such skills involve the ability and judgement an individual will have in working with others, decision making and aid activities. Transferable skills can be applied to many different situations and as such are a good indication of the capability an individual has in handling tasks.

Assessing workforce skills will help you to evaluate the existing skills, knowledge and competencies of your employees. This can be done in a number of ways such as through annual

reviews, commissioning outward testing and assessment which can be set against national standards, and comparing the skills invested in your employees against other entities in your industry.

When it comes to providing the best output for your business and maintaining a steady stream of profitability, assessing your workforce's skills and capabilities is a key element to achieving these goals. Today's modern and fast-paced business environment means that continuous improvement and staying ahead of the competition are essential. Ensuring that your workforce's skills and capabilities are aligned with the business objectives is a difficult task. However, it is required for any enterprise that is aiming for success.

9.2. Implementing Training and Development Programs

Surveys have shown that many employees leave their companies due to a lack of development opportunities and the ability to learn new skills. This is alarming because a revolving door of employees can be very costly and detrimental to an organization's success. This is where effective training and, in particular, a willingness to provide training can have a big impact. In today's business environment, employers and employees alike are well aware that in most cases, employment will not be for life. People move between jobs more now than ever before, and so employees are seeking the opportunity within that job to develop themselves and their careers, not just for the sake of the employee, but also for the company. This is where a clear and well-executed training strategy will lead to a positive impact on the enterprise. For businesses, investing in training and development programs may seem a burden, both in terms of time and money. However, the training and development that a company offers for its team is often a key factor in that person deciding whether to stay with the organization long-term - and the cost of retaining a good employee is much lower than that of finding a new one. It's also important to recognize that as businesses change and develop, employees who have received continual training are more likely to be able to adapt and grow into new roles. It's worth mentioning that investing in the continual development of your team also adds to the skill and knowledge within the business and can lead to greater efficiencies, competitive edge, and as a result, increase profitability. There are many different types of training and development programs, which can be implemented in a company, and they can be undertaken both within the organization and through external courses. The main challenge in this sense is to identify what methods will work best, but also the trick comes on how to manage those effectively within the company operations. For instance, a structured training program can be provided by companies themselves and following a successful strategic competency analysis, which identifies skills and knowledge already within the business and areas that need development, a plan can be produced. This is a fabulous assurance method, but more importantly, it ensures all training provided relates to specific business needs. On the other hand, sending team members to an external commercial course may be just as effective, especially if it is a specialist and focused program. However, the costs of sending someone on a course and covering absence may mean that the course and the person attending have to be carefully chosen. In addition, businesses need to pay attention to the training delivery method. In recent years, e-learning has become quite popular and reputable training companies provide constant and adaptable support alongside their interactive resources. It is a cost-effective way of providing inspired learning to employees, at a suitable pace and a convenient time, where people can actually choose when they want to absorb the new knowledge. With the technological advances and the pace businesses are changing and companies are expanding, online training is simply the way forward and provides a good platform for development.

9.3. Enhancing Employee Engagement and Motivation

Effective employee engagement and motivation results in high performing workplaces. This is particularly the case in work environments that are competitive - as most are in this age of advanced technology - where everyone is expected to do more with less. Today, skills are the primary currency of the workplace and it is through staff's skills, knowledge, and abilities that organizational objectives are met. When employees direct these attributes towards organizational success - when they are 'engaged' - the potential for significantly enhanced performance is substantial. But likewise, when

employees are not truly engaged, when they are merely showing up without putting anything extra in, the loss of potential is also substantial; performance, productivity, and, most crucially of all, the realization of competitive potential can be compromised. A primary way is providing opportunities for employees to grow and develop in the interest of both the individual and the organization. When an employee has developed their capabilities, with more required competencies, they will continue to improve experiences and outputs for the organization. The article argues that organizations deliver this and improve engagement with 'talent management strategies'. This is concerned with what is regarded as a more modern approach to the 21st-century organization, whereby the key focus is not only the past and present practices of personnel management and administrative processes, but also recognizing and utilizing the skills and abilities of the workforce as a fundamental resource for the attainment of organizational objectives. This reflects the most modern thinking - that it is not necessarily how much work is done, it is the quality of what is done. It is in 'talent management' strategies that the focus on employee engagement is convincingly cashed. This is a concept of employee engagement that is about getting the right conditions for all members of an organization to excel, so that both the business and its people can achieve their mutual goals. This is especially so in the context of opportunities for growth - where talent is recognized, encouraged, and rewarded, the approach to employee engagement focuses on the improvements of the individual and the interests of the organization in achieving success. If employees give their best, this means greater alignment with organizational success in their improved performance and the fulfillment of their personal professional aspirations and their psychological well-being - in terms of the article this should fuel employee engagement to the virtuous circles discussed.

10. Risk Management

By working through each of the risks in turn, each area of the business is given a thorough health check and a clear plan can be drawn up as to how each risk can be prevented from occurring or how the business can be prepared to deal with the risk. In fact, since one of the definitions of risk is the uncertainty of an economic loss, a good risk management approach can actually reduce the amount of contingency provisions set aside to deal with some common problems. Emergency procedures take account of the fact that a sudden loss of production or sales will result in the need to act quickly and effectively to be able to continue trading or to recover the ground lost. Such procedures cover a range of potential emergencies, such as fire or flood and have the aim of minimizing the effect on the business and returning to normal production as fast as possible.

The first step in effective risk management is to identify and assess the possible risks that may be faced by the business. This includes not only the obvious such as fire or theft, but also the more subtle, such as a key supplier going out of business or a new competitor entering the market. Outlining the probability of each risk occurring and the potential impact is a useful way to prioritize risk management activity. This can be done using a risk assessment table, which lists the potential risks to the business and allows an assessment to be made of the possible economic damage on the one hand and the cost of preventive measures on the other.

Risk management is the process of identifying, assessing and controlling the potential threats to an organization's profitability and providing a framework to leverage opportunities. According to Business Dictionary, risk management is the "identification, analysis and economic control of those risks which can threaten the assets or earning capacity of an enterprise".

10.1. Identifying and Assessing Business Risks

Whilst risks can never be fully eliminated, having processes in place to identify business risks and assess the likelihood of them occurring and potential impact can go a long way to making the risk more manageable and proactive treatment could avoid it becoming an issue. But on the other hand, if the risk was to manifest, the impact can be minimized by earlier recognition, assessment and by putting in place pre-planned actions. There is a wide range of risks that can face a new or growing business, transactional, operational, regulatory, compliance and reputational and more. Transactional risks arise when entering into business transactions with others. Every transaction has some risk

associated with it and the most common types of transactional risks are payment processing risk, where generally, there is a risk of fraudulent transactions in terms of payment processing. Some people might abuse the payment system, using cards that are not for them to use, otherwise known as stolen or counterfeit. By not putting in place measures to protect the processing of payments taken, there is a risk of being out of pocket. Even if someone else was to commit fraud, the company that takes the payment would bear the impact of that transaction. Operational risk is commonly associated with the day-to-day running of a business. This type of risk is the risk of loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems or from external events. These risks could relate to harm to clients from failed products or services, leading to operational losses (and potentially legal action) or may be a loss of essential services such as power-outs or the office/plant getting damaged. An important and often complex part of managing risks is to decide how serious a risk may, its likelihood and how best to mitigate it. Losses can happen if what you are doing initiate legal action monetary loss or fines lead to loss of income, etc and a risk management process aims to identify what losses might arise. Once a list of risk has been produced and shared with relevant personnel, the next step is to grade and prioritize each risk. By taking into consideration the potential amount of loss, the likelihood of it happening and also the graveness of the loss, risks can be given a grade to describe its severity. With this information, it is then possible to target the most important or high-risk areas first and know where to focus initial efforts. By doing this it allows risks to be dealt with in a logical and controlled manner, meaning that scarce resources can be utilized most effectively.

10.2. Implementing Risk Mitigation Strategies

With active risk mitigation, the focus is on steps that can be taken specifically to mitigate the risk of any given hazard. For example, an effort could be made to modify an operation's work so that potential dangers in the operation's system can be reduced. On the other hand, if the risk is from a structural component such as a containment, then passive mitigation will involve what can be done in the design and planning stage to mitigate the rate of risk.

An example of avoidance can be not operating or extending from your normal service if a business feels that they are unable to maintain a good quality service during that risk period. Passing performance is an example of transferring risk to a third party. This might include employing a contractor on a project who then accepts all liabilities for the work as built and placed into service. It's a great risk management method as the organization has effectively transferred risk to someone who has the correct expertise in installing the equipment, so the risk is transferred to the installers. Compensation is a risk as well. This is similar to the passive or active designation of risk management.

There are two main types of risk mitigation, active and passive. Active risk mitigation is an action that involves investigation, processes, and written documents with the objective of reducing the environmental and conditions that can produce certain hazardous conditions. It tends to be based on the combination of monthly routine fire safety inspections combined with documented results. Passive risk mitigation, however, is a system that incorporates fire protection and prevention in the design and build of buildings, along with advanced planning and decision-making techniques, well before any hazardous situation materializes. Good risk mitigation tactics use both types to minimize potential risks. These include avoiding the risk, transferring the risk to an outer party, reducing the negative effect of a certain risk, and retaining some of the risk.

Risk mitigation is a strategy that aims to reduce the probability of certain bad events occurring and decrease the seriousness of those events should they occur. The method involves retention of risk, if the risks are within an acceptable range, avoidance of risk, or risk controls. The first step in a system of risk reduction is to identify all the ways in which risks are present. Such risks may include temporary loss of business considerations, operational and administrative impacts, spoiling or corruption of data, temporary interruption or degradation of manufacturing or service levels, or temporary inability to produce or operate in the normal manner.

10.3. Ensuring Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery Plans

The critical final part of a risk management strategy is to make sure that disaster recovery plans and business continuity planning are in position. Disaster recovery plans will make sure that all crucial business operations may continue if the worst should occur. The disaster recovery plan must be periodically tested to highlight deficiencies, guaranteeing the organization's capacity to survive a disaster and provide operational direction, which will be necessary when the plan is effectuated. Execution processes are broadly similar in terms of disaster recovery planning across most industries and good practice usually involves the following steps: risk assessment, risk management, development, assignment, documentation, periodic testing and full maintenance. On the other hand, business continuity planning will make sure that the organization can continue to trade regardless of the emergency which occurs. By setting up and acting upon the availability marketing plans, great emphasis is placed on the brand and the technology and the manner in which services or products are offered. Similarly, the team responsible for business continuity planning must make sure that the operational targets are met and the crisis management teams are sufficiently equipped to handle any situation. Business continuity plans take the procedures and instructions produced through disaster recovery planning and develop a procedure that will make sure that the organization is able to continue to trade. In addition, by responding to opportunities in an active manner, business continuity planning may also provide the ground for improved standard in day-to-day customer service and the ability for businesses to achieve their strategic objectives.